

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE IN EDUCATION

Kaniyazova Aydaulet Bakhtiyarovna

Trainee-teacher of Karakalpak State University

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Abstract. Pragmatic competence plays a pivotal role in effective communication across diverse social contexts. It encompasses the ability to use language appropriately, taking into account cultural norms, social conventions, and the intentions of interlocutors. This competence goes beyond mere linguistic knowledge, emphasizing the understanding and application of implicit meanings, politeness strategies, and conversational implicatures. In both personal and professional spheres, pragmatic competence facilitates successful interactions, enhances relationship-building, and fosters mutual understanding. This article explores the significance of pragmatic competence in fostering effective communication, managing social interactions, and navigating cultural differences, highlighting its critical role in today's interconnected and multicultural world.

Keywords: pragmatic competence, effective communication, social interaction, cultural sensitivity, language proficiency

Introduction. In today's interconnected and multicultural world, the ability to communicate effectively extends beyond mere linguistic proficiency. Pragmatic competence, defined as the aptitude to use language appropriately in various social contexts, plays a crucial role in facilitating successful interactions and understanding [2]. It encompasses the ability to navigate cultural nuances, interpret implicit meanings, and employ appropriate speech acts according to situational norms. This introductory chapter explores the significance of pragmatic competence in enhancing communication effectiveness, promoting social harmony, and fostering mutual understanding across diverse interpersonal and professional settings. By examining its pivotal role in interpersonal relationships, cultural competence, and conflict resolution, this paper underscores the indispensable value of pragmatic competence in contemporary communication practices.

Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to use language effectively in social contexts, beyond just knowing the grammar and vocabulary. It involves understanding the social rules, cultural norms, and implied meanings in communication. There are some reasons why pragmatic competence is important:

1. **Effective Communication:** It helps in conveying intended meanings clearly and appropriately, considering the context and the relationship between speakers.

2. **Social Interaction:** Pragmatic competence allows individuals to navigate various social situations, such as formal or informal settings, with appropriate language and behavior.

3. **Cultural Sensitivity:** It promotes understanding of cultural differences in communication styles, which is crucial in multicultural and global environments [5].

4. **Conflict Resolution:** It enables individuals to manage and resolve conflicts through effective negotiation and persuasion.

5. **Career Success:** In professional settings, pragmatic competence contributes to building relationships, leadership skills, and overall success in teamwork and collaborations.

6. **Personal Relationships:** It supports building and maintaining personal relationships by ensuring mutual understanding and respect.

It is clear that pragmatic competence is essential for both personal and professional interactions, enhancing overall communication effectiveness and fostering positive social connections.

Examples showcasing the importance of pragmatic competence abound in everyday interactions:

1. **Workplace Communication:** A manager effectively uses indirect speech to provide constructive feedback, maintaining team morale and productivity.

2. **Cross-Cultural Negotiation:** During international business negotiations, executives navigate differing communication styles and expectations to reach mutually beneficial agreements.

3. **Customer Service:** A customer service representative adapts their language and tone to address diverse customer needs respectfully and efficiently.

4. **Social Media Interactions:** Users demonstrate sensitivity to context and audience when engaging in online discussions, avoiding misunderstandings and promoting constructive dialogue.

5. **Educational Settings:** Teachers employ varying levels of formality and politeness strategies to engage students from different cultural backgrounds, fostering inclusive learning environments [1].

6. Healthcare Communication: Healthcare providers communicate medical information clearly and empathetically, considering patients' cultural beliefs and preferences.

These examples illustrate how pragmatic competence enhances communication efficacy across diverse contexts, fostering understanding, cooperation, and positive outcomes.

Conclusion. Pragmatic competence stands as a cornerstone in effective communication, transcending linguistic proficiency to encompass the nuanced understanding and application of social and cultural norms. Throughout this discussion, we have explored how pragmatic competence facilitates clear and respectful communication, fosters harmonious social interactions, and enables individuals to navigate diverse cultural landscapes with sensitivity and efficacy. In both personal relationships and professional environments, this competence not only enhances mutual understanding but also cultivates trust and facilitates conflict resolution. As societies become increasingly interconnected, the ability to interpret implicit meanings, employ appropriate speech acts, and adapt communication styles becomes ever more crucial. Emphasizing the importance of pragmatic competence ensures that individuals can engage meaningfully across cultural boundaries, contributing to inclusive and effective communication practices in today's globalized world.

References:

1. Choraih, M. A., Loutfi, A., & Mansoor, A. (2016). The importance of pragmatic competence in the EFL curriculum: Application and implications. In Arab World English Journal, December 2016 ASELS Annual Conference Proceedings.
2. Domaneschi, F., & Bambini, V. (2020). Pragmatic competence. In The Routledge handbook of philosophy of skill and expertise (pp. 419-430). Routledge.
3. Kasper, G. (1996). The development of pragmatic competence. *Toegepaste Taalwetenschap in Artikelen*, 55(1), 103-120.
4. Tello Rueda, Y. (2006). Developing pragmatic competence in a foreign language. *Colombian applied linguistics journal*, (8), 169-182.
5. Kaniyazova, A. (2024). INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND MISUNDERSTANDINGS IN PRAGMATICS. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(4), 87-90.
6. Bakhtiyarovna, K. A. (2024). GENDER DIFFERENCES IN LANGUAGE USE AND POLITENESS STRATEGIES. *American Journal of Philological Sciences*, 4(04), 17-23.